

THE CONTENT OF DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING SKILLS IN FUTURE EDUCATORS BASED ON PHILOSOPHICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of developing logical thinking skills in future teachers, the methodology for developing logical thinking skills in future teachers based on philosophical education, and the effectiveness of developing logical thinking skills in future teachers. Also, methodological aspects of developing logical thinking skills in future teachers based on philosophical education are analyzed.

Key words: pedagogical, theoretical and methodological basis, competence, improvement, technological, model, methodological system, logical thinking, skill, concept, judgment, motivational and axiological, cognitive, problem-based learning methods, interactive technologies.

Introduction.

The importance of philosophy lessons in shaping logical thinking among future teachers is considerable. An analysis of the literature on the methodology of teaching the subject *Philosophy* shows that the assimilation of knowledge, its conscious acceptance in cognitive and practical activity, and its retention in memory are achieved in the form of applying knowledge and methods of activity either according to a model or in analogous situations. The development of logical thinking among future teachers, as in current pedagogical practice, must be ensured not only at the initial two levels but at all levels.

Literature review and methods.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of developing logical thinking skills among future teachers, the methodology of cultivating such skills through philosophy education, and related issues have been studied by J.T. Dillon, J.D. Gobert, O.J. Lindberg, A.D. Olofsson, C.F. Conrad, O.V. Alikseyeva, E.V. Veselovskaya, N.A. Garulya, V.S. Yegorina, N.A. Kolmakova, M.M. Tesheva, A. Abduqodirov, M.Kh. Baybayeva, M.U. Qochqorov, J.S. Iskenderov, Z.T. Nishonova, F.A. Rahmatova, G.A. Nazarova, and D.F. To'xtasinov, among others.

Results and discussion.

In teaching the subject *Philosophy*, adhering to the principles of developing logical thinking skills in future teachers is appropriate to the intended objectives. For this, achieving effectiveness in thinking is required when

fulfilling the educational, upbringing, and developmental goals of the learning process.

Classifying tasks according to forms of logical thinking makes it possible to distinguish the main system of ideas, practice them, and turn them into reflexive actions. The existence of stable thought forms (concept, judgment, inference) and logical operations (analysis, synthesis, abstraction, comparison, generalization, classification, etc.), as well as the mastery of the rules underlying them, indicate the development of independent thinking. During practice, it is necessary to present examples of learning materials in which these logical processes are fully realized or integratively applied so that students can understand them.

To develop logical thinking to the level of distinguishing reproductive, exploratory, problem-role, and creative types, tasks must be interconnected. For the learner, a single task may appear at different levels of complexity depending on the stage of study.

- Receptive tasks include memorizing acquired knowledge, solving algorithmic problems, studying tests, and peer evaluation.

- Exploratory tasks of the first level of complexity: identifying facts and describing them; listing and characterizing methods of analysis and synthesis; comparing and distinguishing; solving classification tasks in pairs; differentiating historical events from socially or professionally significant events.

- Exploratory tasks of the second level: determining, clarifying, and generalizing interrelations of facts (cause, effect, influence, devotion, etc.); transfer (translation, transformation); narration, posing questions, formulating problems; making choices, etc.

- Problem-role tasks of the third level: practical application; solving problem situations; proving, justifying, and verifying problems based on personal observation; evaluation; considering historical experience and socio-cultural orientation in finding effective solutions; comparing different perspectives on the same event; constructing existing forms of scientific texts.

- Creative exploratory and problem-role tasks of the fourth level: induction, deduction, writing reports and lectures, independent work, moral resolution of empirical data and phenomena; solving complex problem situations through intuitive approaches; grasping the essence of open-structured complex problems; collective problem-solving; selecting forms of communication during group problem-solving; addressing problems related to future professional

activity. Depending on the degree of complexity, such tasks are studied in several stages, but they can also be solved according to the principle of approach.

Many authors emphasize the skills associated with the motivational component of logical thinking. However, in our view, attention should also be given to skills related to information consumption. In this regard, M.B. Urazova identified the following skills associated with preparing students for project activity, which are important to consider:

- the ability to set goals and organize the process of achieving them, as well as to explain one's own purpose;
- formulating tasks of logical thinking and putting forward hypotheses;
- independently acquiring knowledge;
- analyzing one's own learning and cognitive activity;
- self-assessment;
- presenting research results in oral and written form.

The concept of "level" refers to the quantitative indicators or developmental state of a given phenomenon. For our study, it is particularly important to define the boundaries of the levels of development of logical thinking skills, from minimum to maximum.

Research on logical thinking skills shows that most scholars distinguish low, medium, and high levels of development. Pedagogical literature describes the levels of assimilation as follows: (1) acquaintance — the ability of the student to recognize, differentiate, and coordinate objects and processes under study; (2) reproduction — reproductive activity; (3) formation of skills and competencies — productive activity; (4) creative level. We consider it appropriate to define the levels of development of logical thinking skills as reproductive, productive, and creative.

Conclusion.

Based on interest and need for knowledge, mastery of strategies and algorithms of cognitive activity, acquisition of knowledge and experience of using cognitive tools, analysis of the results and scope of cognitive activity, as well as the analysis of criteria, indicators, and levels, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The concept of "criteria for assessing the level of development of logical thinking skills" was clarified as a qualitative indicator of personal development that reflects various manifestations of cognitive activity (performing real

cognitive tasks — acquiring, processing, memorizing, and applying information) over a certain period.

2. It was substantiated that it is appropriate to use criteria for assessing logical thinking skills among students in the same way as for their components: motivational-evaluative, cognitive, process-activity, and reflexive-evaluative.

3. The content of indicators of scientific-philosophical worldview was revealed for each criterion.

4. As indicators of scientific activity, the developmental levels of logical thinking skills among future teachers (reproductive, productive, and creative) were defined.

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